

Negative Kinetic Energy and Entanglement in Quantum Bound States

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In (1), an explanation of the quantum feature of a bound state which allows for a particle to exist in a classically forbidden region and have negative kinetic energy is given. Specifically, (1) suggests that although classical mechanics represents kinetic and potential energy by numbers, quantum mechanics treats them as operators and that this is at the heart of the above curious situation.

In this note, we consider this quantum feature from a different point of view. We note that even if one uses an operator for kinetic energy in quantum mechanics, in the free particle case, which uses a wavefunction of $\exp(ipx)$, kinetic energy is always positive and exactly equal to its classical counterpart. Thus, we suggest that measurements occur using $\exp(ipx)$. The problem is that there is an intrinsic length \hbar/p linked with $\exp(ipx)$ and that it exists for all x , even though p is a single value (i.e. there is no acceleration). This makes it usual to use $\exp(ipx)$ in a description of a bound state, but given that it is the function linked with measurement, we argue that it must be present, in fact, a variety of $\exp(ipx)$ s must be present. One must then somehow associate an average kinetic energy with each x , because an exact kinetic energy from one of the $\exp(ipx)$ s does not exist at a sharp x point.

To do this, we suggest that quantum mechanics uses something which does not have a classical analogue, namely the entangled state, $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, of various free particle states. To measure the kinetic energy of a particle as an exact number, as in classical mechanics, one would have to break the entangled state, i.e. knock out a particle such that it is in an $\exp(ipx)$ state. In such a case, this particle could be anywhere because $\exp(ipx)$ holds for all x . One may see that the bound state is actually an entangled one because the kinetic energy of the knocked out particle may actually be higher than the average energy of the bound state.

The point we make, however, is that for $\exp(ipx)$, the kinetic energy is always positive even though there is an operator $-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx$. It is only the kinetic energy of the entangled state which may be negative outside the classical turning points. An entangled state, however, is not a classical state with a single kinetic energy which is positive. As a result, we suggest that the quantum bound state is described in terms of an entangled state which does not map to a classical state. The quantum free particle, on the other hand, maps to a classical state in terms of its momentum and kinetic energy, but cannot describe a bound state by itself in the quantum problem. (Furthermore, we argue that the classical turning points as sharp points is really an average feature as the potential $V(x)$ may be thought of as $\text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$.)

Negative Kinetic Energy and Quantum Bound States from the Point of View of (1)

It is noted in (1) that for a classically bound particle:

$$\text{Kinetic energy} + \text{potential energy} = E \quad ((1)) \quad (\text{nonrelativistic treatment})$$

Furthermore, kinetic energy and potential energy as well as E are real numbers and kinetic energy must be positive. A particle cannot exist outside the classical turning points and so its kinetic energy is 0 at the turning points.

In a quantum bound state, matters are very different as noted in (1). It is pointed out that a particle may exist outside the classical turning points and that its kinetic energy may be negative in such a region. The reason for this unusual situation, as given in (1), is that kinetic energy and energy are no longer numbers, but operators.

We consider the situation from a different point of view and argue that one measures kinetic energy in quantum mechanics for a free particle. This free particle is represented by the wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ which exists for all x and its kinetic energy is always positive. Thus, a quantum bound state is represented by an entangled state which does not have a classical analogue. This entangled state may have a negative kinetic energy and exist outside the classical turning points. In such a view, the classical turning points are average points themselves because one may write: $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$.

One may physically measure a particle outside the classical turning point, but if one wants a specific kinetic energy measurement (and not entangled average), then the particle is in an $\exp(px)$ state which always has positive kinetic energy.

Quantum Free Particle State

We argue that a quantum free particle state, represented by $\exp(ipx)$, is fundamental because it is associated with an exact momentum and kinetic energy value. It is directly linked to a measurement and so is an important object. In terms of momentum and kinetic energy, a free particle is completely consistent with a classical particle. In other words, $p^2/2m$ (nonrelativistic kinetic energy) is always positive for both even if one measures it for $\exp(ipx)$ using an operator. A key feature, however, is that if one is restricted to measuring $\exp(ipx)$, this quantity exists for all x and so one cannot have it vanish easily within classical turning points. Furthermore, $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with an exact p and $p^2/2m$, but with a spatial width of \hbar/p and so one cannot really think of this object as being restricted within a classical $dx \rightarrow 0$. This begs the question: How may one possibly describe a quantum bound state if one must use $\exp(ipx)$'s?

Quantum Bound State

We suggest that a quantum bound state is an entangled state of $\exp(ipx)$ s, i.e.

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

It must be described in terms of an entangled state which is not a direct analogue to the classical bound state. The classical bound state represents, to first order, a free particle with $p(x)p(x)/2m$ in each dx . The quantum entangled state does not. The entangled state is a completely different entity, but must be written in terms of free particle states, $\exp(ipx)$, because these may be measured. To measure a specific $\exp(ipx)$, however, one must break the entangled state, i.e. the bound state. From ((2)) one may see that $p^2/2m$ for this measured state could actually be greater than E_{ave} . Furthermore, the particle could be found outside the

classical turning points. In such a case, the kinetic energy associated with $W(x)$ would be considered to be negative to cancel with $V(x)W(x)$ to create $E W(x)$ (as in the case of a simple harmonic oscillator with $V(x) = .5kx$).

One may ask whether an entangled state has any common features with a classical bound state. There are both common features and different ones.

Different Features

1. A quantum bound state has quantized energy and so only a set of discrete energies are allowed unlike the classical case.
2. Even though the average quantum kinetic energy, $-\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$, for the entangled state within classical turning points exactly equals its classical counterpart, classically one may measure a particle at x , while measuring a free particle means breaking the quantum bound state and an $\exp(ipx)$ may exist anywhere in space.
3. A quantum particle may be found outside the classical turning points, unlike its classical counterpart.

Similarity

1. The average kinetic energy $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ for an entangled state is exactly equal to its classical counterpart.

Negative Kinetic Energy Outside Classical Turning Points

If one considers the quantum equation:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + V(x) W(x) = E_n W(x) \quad ((3))$$

then given that $\exp(ipx)$, the free particle measurable function, one would expect $W(x)$ to exist in all of space. There is an exception to this, namely an infinite well potential, but this requires the various $\exp(ipx)$ which exist outside the potential region to create an entangled state which has $W(x)=0$ outside the infinite potential. To be continuous with the inside of the box with no potential, one must have $W(x)=0$ at the walls of the box. (2)

One may try to apply this scenario to a non-infinite well potential. If one imagines some energy E , one has classical turning points which represent a box so to speak. $W(x) = 0$ outside these turning points and $W(x) \neq 0$ from the inside at the turning points regardless of $V(x)$.

One then has problems satisfying ((3)) within the box because the wavefunction is often not 0 at these turning points, but rather a peak which dies down outside the classical turning points.

As a result, if $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with a measurable $pp/2m$, one expects that one may measure $\exp(ipx)$ at any x , suggesting a presence outside of the classical turning points. Furthermore, given that one only has $\exp(ipx)$ as a measurable and the presence of \hbar/p for each $\exp(ipx)$, it seems that one must have a new state, called an entangled state, which somehow allows one to have an average kinetic energy at each x within the turning points, even though this is not measured, but rather an $\exp(ipx)$ is, but not at a precise x . Thus, classical

energies within the turning points can only be accounted for by such an entangled state which has no classical analogue. The classical analogue is the free particle $\exp(ipx)$ (to an extent) which always has a positive kinetic energy, even if one uses an operator $-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ to measure it. The notion of an operator measuring kinetic energy does not seem to be the key issue, we argue, but rather the existence of the entangled state.

Outside the classical turning points one must still have the same E , so with $V(x)$ present (as in the case of an oscillator $V(x) = .5kxx$) one must have:

$$-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W < 0 \quad ((4))$$

Given that W does not represent a classical state, there is in a sense no issue with ((4)). If one makes a measurement, one breaks the bound state and finds an $\exp(ipx)$ which always has a positive kinetic energy. The issue seems to be that a classical analogue is $\exp(ipx)$ (which always has $pp/2m > 0$), but now $pp/2m$ may be $> E$ and it can be at any x . One does not follow the particle in time as in classical mechanics, but rather has a kind of resonance entangled state. This seems like a curious situation, but one might suggest that it follows from the potential $V(x)$ also really being an average, i.e. $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$. If $V(x)$ is seen as an average, then there is no reason why KE should not be one as well, but this must be linked with a measurement approach and manner of calculating KE_{ave} . Furthermore, if $V(x)$ is really an average, then each $\exp(ikx)$ is associated with an \hbar/k and one does not really have a precise turning point in the first place.

We suggest that the measurement is for an $\exp(ipx)$ which may appear at any x and that the average KE must be calculated using the notion of an entangled state, i.e.

$$KE_{ave} = -\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is not an approach used in classical mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, while (1) suggests that negative kinetic energy in a bound state (linked with the wavefunction) follows from operators, not real numbers, being used for kinetic energy and energy, we suggest that a free quantum particle $\exp(ipx)$, even using operators, always yields a positive $pp/2m$. $\exp(ipx)$ is a classical analogue to a certain extent as it is linked with precise p and $pp/2m$ measurements. To describe a bound state in quantum mechanics, one must create an entangled state $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, which is not a usual classical average. This state is linked with $\exp(ipx)$'s because these are measured through breaking the entangled state to obtain a particular $\exp(px)$. The entangled state has the property that $KE_{ave} = -\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ is exactly the classical kinetic energy. Given that $W(x)$ is created from $\exp(ipx)$ and that $\exp(ipx)$ s exist at all x values, $W(x)$ does not vanish at classical turning points and so one may $KE_{ave} < 0$. This KE_{ave} , however, does not apply to the classical analogue $\exp(ipx)$, but rather to the entangled state and so one should not compare apples with oranges so to speak.

References

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